

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

Grant Agreement No. 870626

Deliverable Title	D7.2 Project's brand identity, communication kit and website
Deliverable Lead:	SSSA
Partner(s) involved:	LIBER
Related Work Package:	WP7 Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach
Related Task:	T7.1.2 Branding, communication kit, website development and the stakeholders' platform
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Other Author(s):	Martina Torma (LIBER)
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870626

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v.01	15/02/2020	Draft created	Caterina Sganga
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v.03	29/02/2020	Draft final version finalized	Caterina Sganga

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1 Executive Summary

Deliverable 7.2 is related to *WP7 - Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach, Task 7.1 Analysis of stakeholder landscape, Engagement and Outreach activities, Subtask 7.1.2 - Branding, communication kit, website development and the stakeholders' platform*. This document reports the work related to the following material developed by SSSA and LIBER:

- project logo;
- PowerPoint template and standard project presentation;
- brochure template;
- poster template;
- introductory video and related intro and end slides;
- project website;
- deliverable's template;
- letterhead.

The above listed communication materials are available to and ready to be used by the whole consortium. However, some of them may be subject to slight modifications in the forthcoming months.

The project website will be subject of continuous updates during the entire project lifecycle.

SSSA and LIBER will be in charge for promptly communicating and storing any related updates and will supervise the correct use of project brand and material for the entire project duration and beyond.

2 Logos

A horizontal standard logo and a vertical one for social media use are provided and stored in the project internal shared folder (Dropbox). The font of the standard logo is Uniform Black. Actually available versions are: full colour, ai, jpg, and png, 300 dpi and 600 dpi.

Logos pdf versions are attached as Annex 1a and Annex 1b to this document.

3 Presentations

Presentations to create awareness of the importance of ReCreating Europe's findings and best practices developed as well as of the stakeholder's platform are a key dissemination activity aiming to reach a wide audience and the project mission endorsement. A project presentation template is available for the use of the consortium in dissemination events. It will also be uploaded both to the project website and to the project social media accounts.

Presentations are attached as Annex 2a and Annex 2b to this document.

4 Brochure

One of the key dissemination tools of ReCreating Europe project is the promotional brochure of the project. It will be disseminated in both electronic and printed format in all networking events that will be organised and attended by the project consortium (i.e. conferences, workshops, etc.). Though it is a traditional dissemination mean, it is still relevant because it achieves to inform about the project key goals and intended outcomes in a concise and efficient way.

ReCreating Europe's brochure has the form of a tri fold flyer of 29,7x21cm (A4) created with Microsoft Office Publisher. It includes the project title and the logo, the project key data info, its mission and target impacts, its objectives, the work plan, the Consortium and the Coordinator's contact details, the kick-off meeting photo of the consortium, etc. It will be updated as soon as outcomes are available, to include other key promotional info.

Project brochure is attached as Annex 3 to this document.

5 Poster

ReCreating Europe's poster gives a snapshot of the project and aims to be self-explanatory. It includes:

- The project logo;
- The logo of the EU and the communication disclaimer;
- The Consortium and their logos;
- Project's concept, goals, impacts, action plan;
- The link to the social media;
- Pictures and graphics associated to the project context.

The project poster is designed and produced in A4 size and will be then enlarged at the printout stage.

The initial version of the project poster is attached as Annexes 4 to this document.

6 Introductory video

In order to increase the visibility and public acknowledgement of the ReCreating Europe, a project YouTube channel is just created and needs to be implemented,

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCmc6HzXrwyj33f50vFq7u0Q>

and a short introductory video is prepared to be embedded on the website,

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCmc6HzXrwyj33f50vFq7u0Q>.

This video may be replaced by another improved version to be prepared in the forthcoming months.

Project video intro and end slides are attached as Annexes 5a and 5b to this document.

7 Website

A project web domain has been registered (<http://www.recreating.eu>) and a web site has been created by SSSA with WordPress 5.0.8. The beta version can be viewed here: <http://makepress-01.it/>. The site and related contents are still under development and implementation; hence, it is not published yet. It is maintained by the ICT service in SSSA, but the project members will be able to update its content using their personal accounts.

The current information is organized through a simple standard menu, which has actually a few items to be modified and yet accessible only by the members of the project:

- HOME/ReCreating Europe - The landing page provides the basic information on the project and its goals. It will provide latest news and snippets provided by the Twitter and Facebook accounts.

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- PEOPLE/Consortium – This page provides an overview of the project multi-disciplinary consortium and partners' expertise. The links associated to the logos will give access to the partner's institutional web sites.
- WORK PACKAGES – This page summarizes each Work Package, including partners involved and expected releases.
- ACTIVITIES – This page makes an outline of the project research and innovation and outreach activities.
- CONTACT US – This page includes contact details and a web contact form for direct communication with project partners.
- FORUM – This area will feature an online community (Stakeholders' Platform) to discuss project topics. The Stakeholders' platform will be a key element of the project's website and will operate as the main entry point of interaction with the several stakeholder groups. There they will be able to find material targeted to them, but also have the opportunity and be encouraged to upload and showcase their own material, thus contributing to the resources of the project. Best practices and policy recommendations will be accessible for them according to the FAIR (Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable) principles. The platform will act as a transparent forum for bottom-up proposals, along with or in addition to the inputs provided by stakeholders during the participatory research activities conducted by each vertical WP.

The project website will host contents also from the social media platforms (Twitter project account set; LinkedIn and Facebook project accounts still under development) in order to raise awareness and maximise visibility. Social medias will play an important role in the development of the stakeholders' community.

Project website's screenshots are attached as Annex 6 to this document.

8 Deliverable's template

Deliverable's template is attached as Annex 7 to this document.

9 Letterhead

Project's letterhead template is attached as Annex 8 to this document.

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10 Conclusions

Deliverable 7.2 is complementary to the Deliverable 7.1 Engagement and Outreach Strategy. The purpose of this document is to report the project visual identity, website and communication materials developed and under development.

The initial content used for the communication materials is based on the current status of the project. Though the goals will remain the same, the content may slightly change while the project will be progressing and tangible results of the work performed will be available. In order to reflect the work progress in the project, at least one update of the brochure and the poster will happen before the end of the second year (M18) (whereas intermediate improvements may happen as well), while the website and social media contents will be continuously updated.

All updated versions of the brochure and the poster will be made available to public (in digital form) through the project web site (www.recreating.eu).

Annexes 1-18

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ReCreating Europe

D7.2 - Annex 2a

ReCreating Europe

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Pianificazione e attività

D7.2 - Annex 2b

RECREATING EUROPE

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

Project overview

Rationale, methodology, objectives, work plan

Our roadmap

- The consortium
- Project overview: background, concept, objectives, ambition
- Expected impacts
- Work plan

The consortium

Sant'Anna
Scuola Universitaria Superiore Pisa

IVIR
Instituut voor Informatierecht
Institute for Information Law

UNIVERSITY OF AMSTERDAM

**University
of Glasgow**

CREATE

ALEXANDER VON HUMBOLDT
INSTITUTE FOR INTERNET
AND SOCIETY

Ligue des Bibliothèques
Européennes de Recherche
Association of European
Research Libraries

**Maynooth
University**
National University
of Ireland Maynooth

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI
DI TRENTO

UNIVERSITY OF TARTU

UNIVERSITY OF
COPENHAGEN

Background and concept

- Crafting EU copyright in rapidly changing society
 - **New models** of creation, dissemination, consumption of cultural and creative content; **new actors** in the value chain
 - 20 years of **EU harmonization** tackling structural and regulatory constraints
 - Pitfalls
 - Regulatory → fragmentation; uncertainties; lack of flexibility and adaptability; balancing issues; weak link with cultural and media policies
 - Market → fragmentation; inefficiencies; distortion in competition; abuses
- Four parallel phenomena

Background and concept (ii)

Concept: general goals

- Ground-breaking contribution to the understanding and management of copyright in the DSM
- Advancing discussion on how IPRs can be best regulated to facilitate **access** to, **consumption** of and **generation** of **cultural and creative products**
- **Main threads**
 - Access to culture
 - Cultural and creative production
 - Cultural diversity
 - Competitiveness of creative industries
 - Democratization of culture

Concept: general goals (ii)

How-to: four intertwined levels

- Unprecedented **cross-national mapping** of multi-level regulatory responses
- **Innovative methods to measure** impact of digital market on extent, forms, content of production and consumption of cultural/creative goods and services
- Legal, technological and economic **mapping and evaluation** of access-enabling and content-filtering **technologies**
- Set of **policy recommendations** and **best practices to**
 - Remove bottlenecks to digital access, accessibility, creation
 - Exploit of untapped opportunities offered by DSM
 - Embed of copyright and TMPs within EU cultural policies

Objectives

Two domains, four pillars

OBJECTIVES	SPECIFIC RESULTS	DELIVERABLE(S)	KPIS
Mapping	Comparative and EU cross-national mapping of regulatory and private ordering sources impacting on access to culture	D2.1	1 internal database ; 1 report
	Cross-national mapping of legal, economic and tech barriers to access for vulnerable groups	D2.2	Policy brief
	Cross-national mapping of literature and state-of-the-art knowledge on income development of authors and performers in the EU and on copyright reversal	D3.1	1 Report
	Assessment of role of AI machines in producing literary and artistic content, impact on human creators and the protection of literary and artistic productions of AI machines under EU copyright	D3.4; D3.5	2 Reports
	Cross-national mapping of harmonisation of the reproduction and adaptation right and connected exceptions (“legal cartography”) and of the role of EU copyright law in relation to training models for machine learning purposes.	D3.6; D3.7	2 Reports
	Cross-national, mapping of legal framework regulating digitized and digital-born content for Galleries and Museums (GM) and for Libraries and Archives (LA)	D5.1; D5.2	2 Reports
	Comparative and EU cross-national mapping of regulatory and private ordering sources impacting content moderation and removal at scale in online platforms	D6.1	1 Report
Measuring	Agent-based model of cultural consumption in different context	D2.3	1 report on AB results
	Assessing how digitisation and copyright perception shape consumption (survey)	D2.4	1 report (study) and 1 data set
	Case studies on effectiveness of regulatory measures to increase digital access (academics; people with visual impairments)	D2.5	2 reports on case studies and 2 data sets
	Data set and final report on experiences and perceptions of authors and performers throughout EU on digitization and copyright in the DSM.	D3.2; D3.3	1 report and 1 data set
	Assessing how EU law, National law, and platform rules and practices on copyright content moderation and removal impact access to and dissemination of culture online	D6.2	Report (study)
Engaging	Engagement and outreach through engagement activities, dissemination materials, website (incl. Stakeholders’ platform) and other communication means	D7.1; D7.2; D7.3	Reports, website, branding and communications kit
	Building expertise, providing training to stakeholders and urging them to share their own material	D7.4	Training toolkit and building expertise framework
Shaping the future	Best practices for targeted stakeholders and policy recommendations	D2.6; D4.7 D5.7; D6.2	6 best practices and 4 policy recommendations (and related reports)
	Guidelines & FAQs helping GLAMS dealing with laws regulating digital content	D5.3; D5.4, D5.5, D5.6	4 Sets of Guidelines and of FAQs
	Copyright User portal	D4.8	Website

Linked research

Global Online Piracy Study (2017-2018)	GROWINPRO	Imitation and Innovation in the Games Sector(2014-2016)
Film Financing and the Digital Single Market: its Future, the Role of Territoriality and New Models of Financing (2018-2019)	Platform Governance – Discourses, Regulation, Algorithms	copyrightexceptions.eu
Copyright in an Age of Access: Alternatives to Copyright Enforcement (2012-2016)	OpenGLAM	copyrightuser.org
Hosting Intermediary Services And Illegal Content Online (2018)	LODLAM	AHRC/EPSRC/ESRC RCUK Centre for Copyright & New Business Models in the Creative Economy (2012-2018)
DISCIT - Making Persons with Disabilities Full Citizens (2013-2016)	ENUMERATE OBSERVATORY	DIVERCITIES - Governing Urban Diversity: Creating Social Cohesion, Social Mobility and Economic Performance in Today's Hyper-diversified Cities
User Generated Law – Re-Constructing Law in a Knowledge Society (2012-2016)	EnDOW	Study of the content and audiences of culture journalism in Estonia
STYLE - Strategic Transitions for Youth Labour in Europe	RightsStatements.org	

Project overview: methodology

Realms

- Socio-legal analysis
- Economic analysis
- Business models analysis

Tools

- Desk research
- Participatory research
- Other forms of qualitative research
- Quantitative analysis
- Digital (computational) methods
- New narratives and vehicles
- Stakeholders' platform

Ambition

- Ground-breaking goals
- Cutting-edge integration of approaches
- New models for inclusive policy development and implementation
- Overarching scope
- Foundational character

Expected impacts

- **Five goals in line with call challenges**
 - **Domain of knowledge**
 - 1) providing qualitative and quantitative analysis
 - 2) contributing to a better understanding of regulation
 - **Domain of policy**
 - 3) proposing solution, business models and policy recommendations
 - 4) contributing to fairer accessibility of digitised cultural goods and services
 - 5) advise on appropriate levels of harmonisation of copyright and IPR, thereby contributing to the development and deepening of the DSM.

Expected impacts (ii)

- Better comparative knowledge
- New assessment tools
- Evidence-based recommendations

Policy

- Best practices
- Stakeholders' platform & training toolkit
- Increased awareness
- Increased intra- and inter-collaboration

Stakeholders

- Raising awareness on needs of cultural/creative SHs
- Devising strategies for better balance
- Moving towards a closer Union

Societal

Work plan

WP 1 – Management and coordination

WP 2
USERS

WP 3
Authors and
performers

WP 4
Creative
industries

WP 5
GLAM

WP 6
Intermediaries

WP 7 – Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach

72 deliverables, 3 target impacts

- Better comparative knowledge
- New assessment tools
- Evidence-based recommendations

Policy

- Raising awareness on needs of cultural/creative SHs
- Devising strategies for better balance
- Moving towards a closer Union

Societal

- Best practices
- Stakeholders' platform & training toolkit
- Increased awareness
- Increased intra- and inter-collaboration

Stakeholders

The Consortium

Project Coordination

- **Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna**, Pisa, Italy
Caterina Sganga (Coordinator)
Alma Serica (Project Manager)

Partners

- **IVIR, University of Amsterdam**, Amsterdam, Netherlands
- **CREATE, University of Glasgow**, Glasgow, UK
- **Von Humboldt Center for Internet and Society**, Berlin, Germany
- **LIBER**, the Hague, Netherlands
- **Maynooth University**, Maynooth, Ireland
- **University of Trento**, Trento, Italy
- **University of Tartu**, Tartu, Estonia
- **University of Copenhagen**, Copenhagen, Denmark
- **University of Szeged**, Szeged, Hungary

This project is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under GA no. 870626

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

 ReCreating Europe

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WP 1 – Management and coordination

WP 2 USERS

WP 3 Authors and performers

WP 4 Creative industries

WP 5 GLAM

WP 6 Intermediaries

WP 7 – Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach

ReCreating Europe is a H2020 Research and Innovation project **coordinated by Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna**.

The project aims to tackle the major challenges that prevent the **creation of a system of sustainable norms for digital copyright**.

With its **multi-disciplinary approach**, bringing together

- researchers,
- practitioners,
- stakeholders,

ReCreating Europe will deliver **ground-breaking contributions** towards a clear understanding of what makes a **regulatory framework** that promotes culturally **diverse production**, and optimizes **inclusive access and consumption**.

10 partners and 8 EU countries to build a multi-disciplinary, diverse, gender-balanced consortium having a unique blend of expertise and competences in the fields of **intellectual property, information law, economics, management, sociology of innovation, communication and media studies, computer science, geography, history, and policy studies**.

The universities, research centers and associations working on ReCreating Europe are all leading experts in their sectors, supported by strong research networks, and featuring a long and successful track record in policy-oriented studies and stakeholders' engagement.

ReCreating Europe's unique comprehensive focus on five key groups of stakeholders - **individual authors and performers, creative industries, cultural and heritage institutions, Intermediaries, end-users** - allows it to assess needs along intertwined research patterns, while its multi-disciplinary innovative approach joins different methodologies within the framework of **participatory research strategies**.

Project acronym: ReCreating Europe

Grant number: 870626

Call ID: H2020-SC6-GOVERNANCE-2019

Starting date: 1st January 2020

Duration: 3 years

Partners: 10 from 8 countries

Funding: 3,087,928.75 €

ReCreating Europe has four main objectives

1. MAPPING

- Laws, court decisions, regulations, policies, contracts
- Stakeholders' conducts and strategies

2. MEASURING the impact of digitisation on production, distribution, consumption of cultural and creative goods and services

3. ASSESSING TECHNOLOGIES

Legal and technological mapping of TPMs and content-filtering algorithm; evaluation of impact on cultural diversity and access to culture

4. ENGAGING AND SHAPING THE FUTURE

Stakeholders' platform; delivery of best practices and policy recommendations

ReCreating Europe

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

CONCEPT

GOALS

IMPACTS

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better comparative knowledge New assessment tools Evidence-based recommendations <p>Policy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Best practices Stakeholders' platform & training toolkit Increased awareness Increased intra- and inter-collaboration <p>Stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raising awareness on needs of cultural/creative SHs Devising strategies for better balance Moving towards a closer Union <p>Societal</p>
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ACTION PLAN

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870626

ReCreating Europe

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible and creative Europe

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Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

DISCOVER THE PROJECT

Technologies enable unprecedented democratization of cultural practices and the production and use of IP. The creation of an effective system of sustainable norms for digital copyright is a major challenge due to four phenomena: copyright complexity, sidestepping, knowledge gap, and awareness gap. With its multi-disciplinary approach, bringing together researchers, practitioners and stakeholders, reCreating Europe will deliver ground-breaking contributions towards a clear understanding of what makes a regulatory framework that promotes culturally diverse production, and optimizes inclusive access and consumption.

The project

MAPPING

reCreating Europe yields unprecedented cross-national maps of (i) multi-level regulatory responses that impact access to culture, cultural production, competitiveness of creative industries, and (ii) coping strategies of stakeholders vis-à-vis IPRs pitfalls and constraints.

MEASURING

reCreating Europe develops innovative qualitative and quantitative methods to measure the impact of digitization on the production and consumption of cultural goods and services. Changing intermediaries, specific creative communities, micro/SMEs and vulnerable users get special attention.

ASSESSING TECHNOLOGIES

reCreating Europe performs a legal and technological mapping and evaluation of TPMs and content-filtering algorithms, and their impact on cultural diversity, access to culture and the generation of cultural value.

SHAPING THE FUTURE

reCreating Europe offers policy recommendations and best practices, aimed at democratizing culture while reinforcing the sustainable development of rich and diverse cultural/ creative industries.

reCreating Europe's unique comprehensive focus on five key groups of stakeholders - individual authors and performers, creative industries, cultural and heritage institutions, intermediaries, end-users - allows it to assess needs along intertwined research patterns, while its multi-disciplinary innovative approach joins different methodologies within the framework of participatory research strategies.

WP2 USERS

Lorem ipsum

WP3 Authors and performers

Lorem ipsum

WP4 Creative Industries

Lorem ipsum

WP5 GLAM

Lorem ipsum

WP6 Intermediaries

Lorem ipsum

Get engaged!

GO TO THE STAKEHOLDERS' PLATFORM

People

10 partners and 8 EU countries to build a multidisciplinary, diverse, gender-balanced consortium having a unique blend of expertise and competences in the fields of intellectual property, information law, economics, management, sociology of innovation, communication and media studies, computer science, geography, history, and policy studies. The universities, research centers and associations working on ReCreating Europe are all leading experts in their sectors, supported by strong research networks, and featuring a long and successful track record in policy-oriented studies and stakeholders' engagement.

Work Packages

reCreating Europe is organized around 2 horizontal work packages (WPs), involving all partners and covering management (WP1) and dissemination, engagement and outreach (WP7) and 5 vertical, stakeholder-based WPs (WP2 to WP6) further subdivided into tasks. WP2 to 6 provide technical and scientific input to WP7, which aims to maximize the expected impacts of the project through proactive engagement and dissemination.

- WP1 – Management and Coordination
- WP2 – End users and access to culture
- WP3 – Authors and performers
- WP4 – Creative industries
- WP5 – GLAM
- WP6 – Intermediaries
- WP7 – Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach

Activities and publications

From January 2020 to December 2022, reCreating Europe will organize a wide range of events, produce various types of research outputs, publish training materials, and proactively engage stakeholders in all its activities.

1

Workshops and conferences

Events organized by or connected to reCreating Europe

2

Engaging stakeholders

Are you a creator, performer, user? A representative of creative industries? Do you work for libraries, galleries, archives, museums or other cultural institutions? Join our forum, learn about our activities and contribute to our research for a better regulatory framework

3

Training

Our training toolkit to raise awareness, train-the-trainers, and help filling knowledge gaps

4

Mapping, measuring, studying

Databases, surveys, interviews, data analysis, statistics, modelling, papers and other fun stuff

5

Shaping the future

Guidelines, recommendations, FAQs for stakeholders and regulators

6

Publications

Our Zenodo repository of publications in open access

D7.2 - Annex 7

Style sheet for report-based deliverables

The document below outlines the typical report-based deliverable structure for ReCreating Europe project and sets the common style for unified reporting under this project. The style is already incorporated in this annex, and therefore Annex A can be used as a template for ReCreating Europe documents.

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

Grant Agreement No. 870626

Deliverable Title	Dx.x Deliverable Title
Deliverable Lead:	Short name of the lead organisation
Partner(s) involved:	Short name of the partners involved
Related Work Package:	WPno WP Title
Related Task/Subtask:	Tx.x.x Task/Subtask Title
Main Author(s):	Name of Author(s) (Short name of the author's organisation)
Other Author(s):	Name of Author(s) (Short name of the author's organisation)
Dissemination Level:	Public/Confidential
Due Delivery Date:	dd.mm.yyyy
Actual Delivery:	dd.mm.yyyy
Project ID	870626
Instrument:	H2020-SC6-GOVERNANCE-2019
Start Date of Project:	01.01.2020
Duration:	36 months

Version history table			
Version	Date	Modification reason	Modifier(s)
v.01			
v.02			
v.03			

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Table of Contents

List of Tables

(when applicable)

List of Figures

(when applicable)

Abbreviation list

(in alphabetical order if there are > 10)

Executive Summary

(text, no more than 1 page)

1. Methodology

(when applicable)

2. Chapters

(reaching up to fourth level of sub-heading maximum)

3. Conclusions

(encompassing future steps)

References

Annexes

(numbered and optional)

Style instructions:

Main Heading (use style: Heading 1, Calibri 16 pt, Normal, Bold)

Content (use style: Calibri 11 pt, Normal, Justified text, Line spacing 1.0)

Sub-Heading (use style: Heading 2, Calibri 14 pt, Normal, Bold)

Content (use style: Calibri 11 pt, Normal, Justified text, Line spacing 1.0)

Third Level Heading (use style: Heading 3, Calibri 14 pt, Normal, Bold)

(use style: Calibri 11 pt, Normal, Justified text, Line spacing 1.0)

For bullets use:

- bullet style
- bullet style

For tables and figures, insert a caption (from References tab, Insert Caption in Captions, choose table or figure accordingly)

D7.2 - Annex 8

